

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART V.

BY TEJENDRA NATH GHOSH.

The synthesis of triazolylquinoline is described.

1:5-Diphenyl-3-hydroxy-1:2:4-triazole has been found to have antipyretic activity (Pieta, *Arch. Int. pharmacodynamie*, 1929, 36, 236), although it is rather toxic. It, therefore, seemed of some interest to synthesise a 1:2:4-triazolylquinoline derivative, which is expected to possess antipyretic activity.

Diacetylthioacetocarbanic acid readily reacts with hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine to yield a 1:2:4-triazole derivative of the type (I) (cf. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 88). When allowed to react further with hydrazine hydrate, the compound (I) furnishes the triazolyl pyrazole derivative (II). The anilide (III), obtained by condensing (I) with aniline, furnishes the triazolylquinoline derivative (IV), when treated with strong sulphuric acid at 110°.

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2-Phenyl-3-keto-5-diacetylmethyl-dihydro-1:2:4-triazole (I, R=Ph).—Phenylhydrazine (5.4 g.) was added to an alcoholic solution of diacetylthioacetocarbamie acid (10.2 g.), when the reaction immediately commenced with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen and rise in temperature. For completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 1½ hours. When cooled, the solution was diluted with water, when a semi-solid mass was obtained. It was triturated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered. The solid crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 105-106°, yield 7 g. (Found: C, 60.64; H, 5.48; N, 16.38. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires C, 60.23; H, 5.01; N, 16.21 per cent). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali.

The acid solution was treated with excess of sodium bicarbonate, when a pasty mass was obtained, which did not solidify even when kept in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid for a long time and could not be crystallised. It is probably the condensation product of (I, R=Ph) with another molecule of phenylhydrazine.

δ-Phenylimido-γ-(2-phenyl-3-ketodihydro-1:2:4)-triazolyl-β-ketopentane (III, R=Ph).—A mixture of aniline (3 g.) and the above compound (I, R=Ph; 8.6 g.) was heated on an oil-bath at 160-70° for 2 hours, when there was elimination of water vapour. The cold molten mass was triturated with alcohol, when a solid was obtained which was washed with ether and crystallised from alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 205-207°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 68.43; H, 5.77; N, 16.52. $C_{19}H_{18}O_2N_4$ requires C, 68.26; H, 5.38; N, 16.76 per cent).

2:4-Dimethyl-3-(2'-phenyl-3'-ketodihydro-1':2':4')-triazolylquinoline (IV, R=Ph).—A solution of the above compound (III, R=Ph; 3 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) was heated on an oil-bath at 110° for one hour, cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The precipitated solid was filtered and after crystallisation from alcohol was found to be the original compound (III, R=Ph). The clear acid solution was treated with excess of sodium bicarbonate, when a solid was obtained, which was purified by dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitating with excess of sodium bicarbonate. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, melting completely at 295° to a thick reddish brown syrup, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 71.79; H, 5.47; N, 17.44. $C_{19}H_{16}ON_4$ requires C, 72.15; H, 5.06; N, 17.72 per cent). It is insoluble in dilute alkali but readily soluble in cold acid.

2:4-Dimethyl-3-(3'-ketodihydro-1':2':4')-triazolylpyrazole (II, R=H).—An alcoholic solution of equimolecular proportions of hydrazine hydrate and

the compound (I, R=H; prepared according to the method of Ghosh, *loc. cit.*), was heated under reflux for about 3 hours, and then diluted with water until the solution was slightly turbid and allowed to cool. The crystalline solid, thus obtained, was further crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 160°. (Found: N, 38.78. $C_7H_9ON_3$ requires N, 39.10 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali and also in cold dilute hydrochloric acid. It does not condense with phenyl isothiocyanate, indicating the absence of any hydrazino group.

δ -Phenylimide- γ -(3-ketodihydro-1:2:4)-triazolyl- β -ketopentane (III, R=H).—A mixture of aniline (3 g.) and the compound (I, R=H; 6 g.) was heated on an oil-bath at 150-55° for about 2 hours, when there was elimination of water vapour. The temperature was raised to 180° for about 15 minutes and the molten mass allowed to cool. It was triturated with cold alcohol, when a solid was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 226-27°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: N, 21.39. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_4$ requires N, 21.70 per cent). It is insoluble in hot concentrated hydrochloric acid and gives a brownish red colouration with ferric chloride.

The above compound was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid at 100° for 30 minutes. The solution was cooled and poured into ice-cold water, when no precipitate was obtained even on long standing. When treated with excess of sodium bicarbonate, the solution remained clear and did not deposit any precipitate. Nothing could be obtained by treating the clear solutions with ether.

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DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

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